

230320 analysis volume FIB SEM stacks Thalassiosira

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```
## [1] "D:/Users/Jhoanell/Documents/~Jhoanell 2025/Labo/Thalassiosira_project/~Thesis work/paper chloro
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 x 9
```

```
## # Groups:   experiment, test, time, phase, genotype, media, organelle [6]
```

```
##   experiment test time phase genotype media organelle volume surface
##   <chr>      <dbl> <dbl> <chr> <chr> <chr> <chr> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 1          1 72 f    Tp    5_Fe cell      41.8 151.
## 2 1          1 72 f    Tp    5_Fe vacuole 14.2 30.7
## 3 1          1 72 f    Tp    5_Fe nucleus 1.64 6.95
## 4 1          1 72 f    Tp    5_Fe chloroplast 5.52 22.1
## 5 1          1 72 f    Tp    5_Fe mitochondria 1.03 10.2
## 6 1          1 72 f    Tp    5_Fe pyrenoid 0.711 6.46
```

```
##   experiment time phase genotype media organelle geometric N value sd
## 1          1 72 f    To 100_Fe chloroplast volume 7 10.8 3.30
## 2          1 72 f    To 100_Fe chloroplast surface 7 45.7 14.72
## 3          1 72 f    To 100_Fe mitochondria volume 6 1.2 0.31
## 4          1 72 f    To 100_Fe mitochondria surface 6 9.5 2.57
## 5          1 72 f    To 100_Fe nucleus volume 1 3.6 NA
## 6          1 72 f    To 100_Fe nucleus surface 1 11.9 NA
##   se ci
## 1 1.25 3.05
## 2 5.56 13.61
## 3 0.13 0.32
## 4 1.05 2.70
## 5 NA NaN
## 6 NA NaN
```

Statistical tests

Normality and variance homogeneity tests

Shapiro-Wilk normality test:

Variance test:

```
##           genotype p_value p_signif p_adj p_adj_signif
## 1 To volume +/-Fe 0.01411 * NA
## 2 To surface +/-Fe 0.003143 ** NA
## 3 Tp volume +/-Fe 0.9239 NA
## 4 Tp surface +/-Fe 0.4286 NA
```

t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 20 x 12
##   media organelle  geometric .y.  group1 group2  n1  n2  statistic  p
##   <fct> <fct>      <fct>   <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>    <dbl>  <dbl>
## 1 100_Fe chloropla~ volume  value To    Tp    11  11    100 8.33e-3
## 2 100_Fe mitochond~ volume  value To    Tp    10  11     43 4.26e-1
## 3 100_Fe nucleus    volume  value To    Tp     3   4     12 5.71e-2
## 4 100_Fe vacuole    volume  value To    Tp     6   8     42 2.00e-2
## 5 100_Fe cell        volume  value To    Tp    11  11     92 4.00e-2
## 6 100_Fe chloropla~ surface value To    Tp    11  11    108 1.04e-3
## 7 100_Fe mitochond~ surface value To    Tp    10  11     19 1.01e-2
## 8 100_Fe nucleus    surface value To    Tp     3   4     11 1.14e-1
## 9 100_Fe vacuole    surface value To    Tp     6   8     41 2.93e-2
## 10 100_Fe cell        surface value To    Tp    11  11     76 3.32e-1
## 11 5_Fe  chloropla~ volume  value To    Tp     9  11     84 7.44e-3
## 12 5_Fe  mitochond~ volume  value To    Tp     9  11     76 4.65e-2
## 13 5_Fe  nucleus    volume  value To    Tp     3   4     12 5.71e-2
## 14 5_Fe  vacuole    volume  value To    Tp     6   8     40 4.26e-2
## 15 5_Fe  cell        volume  value To    Tp     9  11     92 5.36e-4
## 16 5_Fe  chloropla~ surface value To    Tp     9  11     89 1.64e-3
## 17 5_Fe  mitochond~ surface value To    Tp     9  11     21 3.10e-2
## 18 5_Fe  nucleus    surface value To    Tp     3   4     12 5.71e-2
## 19 5_Fe  vacuole    surface value To    Tp     6   8     38 8.13e-2
## 20 5_Fe  cell        surface value To    Tp     9  11     96 8.34e-5
## # i 2 more variables: p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>
```


e cell media 5_Fe ge

t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 20 x 13
##   genotype organelle  geometric .y.  group1 group2  n1  n2 statistic  df
##   <fct>     <fct>     <fct>    <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>    <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 To       chloropla~ volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   9     2.20  11.5
## 2 To       mitochond~ volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe    10   9     0.361  9.46
## 3 To       nucleus    volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe     3   3     0.423  2.41
## 4 To       vacuole    volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe     6   6     1.40   7.65
## 5 To       cell       volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   9     0.180 13.5
## 6 To       chloropla~ surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   9     2.20  10.8
## 7 To       mitochond~ surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe    10   9    -0.103 10.2
## 8 To       nucleus    surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe     3   3     0.329  3.12
## 9 To       vacuole    surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe     6   6     1.43   7.89
## 10 To      cell       surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   9    -1.14  12.3
## 11 Tp      chloropla~ volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     1.19  18.9
## 12 Tp      mitochond~ volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     1.84  19.4
## 13 Tp      nucleus    volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe     4   4     1.16   5.85
## 14 Tp      vacuole    volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe     8   8     2.24  14.0
## 15 Tp      cell       volume  value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     1.15  20.0
## 16 Tp      chloropla~ surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     0.381 18.7
## 17 Tp      mitochond~ surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     1.40  19.9
## 18 Tp      nucleus    surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe     4   4     1.30   4.75
## 19 Tp      vacuole    surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe     8   8     2.27  13.7
## 20 Tp      cell       surface value 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11     0.437 18.8
## # i 3 more variables: p <dbl>, p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>
```


■ chloroplast
 ■ mitochondria
 ■ nucleus
 ■ va

inelle

- chloroplast
- nucleus
- pyrenoid
- cristae
- mitochondria
- vacuole
- thylakoid

I plot as clarisse volume to surface in chloroplast and mitochondria by species and condition:


```
## # A tibble: 6 x 10
## # Groups:   experiment, test, time, phase, genotype, media, geometric [1]
##   experiment test  time phase genotype media organelle geometric value geo_cal
##   <fct>      <fct> <dbl> <chr> <fct>   <fct> <fct>      <fct>      <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 1          1      72 f    Tp      5_Fe cell       volume     41.8  100
## 2 1          1      72 f    Tp      5_Fe vacuole    volume     14.2  33.9
## 3 1          1      72 f    Tp      5_Fe nucleus   volume     1.64  3.93
## 4 1          1      72 f    Tp      5_Fe chloropl~ volume     5.52  13.2
## 5 1          1      72 f    Tp      5_Fe mitochon~ volume     1.03  2.46
## 6 1          1      72 f    Tp      5_Fe pyrenoid  volume     0.711 1.70
```

t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 16 x 13
##   genotype organelle geometric .y. group1 group2 n1 n2 statistic df
##   <fct>    <fct>      <fct> <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 To      chloropla~ volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 9 5.67 15.0
## 2 To      mitochond~ volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 10 9 0.0679 14.0
## 3 To      nucleus    volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 3 3 -0.450 3.58
## 4 To      vacuole    volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 6 6 1.24 6.55
## 5 To      chloropla~ surface geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 9 6.83 14.5
## 6 To      mitochond~ surface geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 10 9 1.29 16.0
## 7 To      nucleus    surface geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 3 3 -0.0714 2.50
## 8 To      vacuole    surface geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 6 6 1.93 9.69
## 9 Tp      chloropla~ volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 11 0.392 20.0
## 10 Tp     mitochond~ volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 11 1.27 20.0
## 11 Tp     nucleus    volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 4 4 0.621 5.60
## 12 Tp     vacuole    volume geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe 8 8 3.03 11.4
```

```

## 13 Tp      chloropla~ surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe      11    11    0.101  19.7
## 14 Tp      mitochond~ surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe      11    11    1.29   19.7
## 15 Tp      nucleus    surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe      4     4     0.866  3.88
## 16 Tp      vacuole    surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe      8     8     3.26   13.6
## # i 3 more variables: p <dbl>, p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>

```


plastid mitochondria nucleus |

Statistical tests

Normality and variance homogeneity tests

Shapiro-Wilk normality test:

```
## # A tibble: 24 x 9
##   genotype media organelle geometric variable statistic      p p.adj p.signif
##   <fct>    <fct> <fct>    <fct>    <chr>    <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr>
## 1 To      100_Fe chloropl~ volume   geo_cal  0.967 0.857 1      ns
## 2 To      100_Fe chloropl~ surface  geo_cal  0.944 0.564 1      ns
## 3 To      100_Fe mitochon~ volume   geo_cal  0.944 0.600 1      ns
## 4 To      100_Fe mitochon~ surface  geo_cal  0.787 0.00995 0.229 **
```

```

## 5 To      100_Fe vacuole  volume  geo_cal    0.882 0.278  1    ns
## 6 To      100_Fe vacuole  surface  geo_cal    0.868 0.218  1    ns
## 7 To      5_Fe  chloropl~ volume  geo_cal    0.956 0.751  1    ns
## 8 To      5_Fe  chloropl~ surface  geo_cal    0.918 0.372  1    ns
## 9 To      5_Fe  mitochon~ volume  geo_cal    0.751 0.00561 0.135 **
## 10 To     5_Fe  mitochon~ surface  geo_cal    0.910 0.315  1    ns
## # i 14 more rows

```

Variance test:

```

##          genotype p_value p_signif p_adj p_adj_signif
## 1 To chloroplast volume +/-Fe 0.4547      NA
## 2 To chloroplast surface +/-Fe 0.03471    *   NA
## 3 To mitochondria volume +/-Fe 0.2897      NA
## 4 To mitochondria surface +/-Fe 0.3181      NA
## 5 Tp chloroplast volume +/-Fe 0.9765      NA
## 6 Tp chloroplast surface +/-Fe 0.7214      NA
## 7 Tp mitochondria volume +/-Fe 0.9001      NA
## 8 Tp mitochondria surface +/-Fe 0.7228      NA

```

t_test for means

```

## # A tibble: 12 x 13
##   genotype organelle  geometric .y.  group1 group2  n1  n2 statistic  df
##   <fct>      <fct>      <fct>  <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>    <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 To      chloropla~ volume  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  9    5.67    15.0
## 2 To      chloropla~ surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  9    6.83    14.5
## 3 To      mitochond~ volume  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    10  9    0.0679  14.0
## 4 To      mitochond~ surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    10  9    1.29    16.0
## 5 To      vacuole    volume  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe     6  6    1.24     6.55
## 6 To      vacuole    surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe     6  6    1.93     9.69
## 7 Tp      chloropla~ volume  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11   0.392   20.0
## 8 Tp      chloropla~ surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11   0.101   19.7
## 9 Tp      mitochond~ volume  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11   1.27    20.0
## 10 Tp     mitochond~ surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe    11  11   1.29    19.7
## 11 Tp     vacuole    volume  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe     8  8    3.03    11.4
## 12 Tp     vacuole    surface  geo_~ 100_Fe 5_Fe     8  8    3.26    13.6
## # i 3 more variables: p <dbl>, p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>

```


vacuole
 media
 100_I

t_test for means

```

## # A tibble: 12 x 12
##   genotype organelle   geometric .y.   group1 group2   n1   n2 statistic
##   <fct>     <fct>         <fct>   <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>   <dbl>
## 1 To       chloroplast  volume  geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    11    9     97
## 2 To       chloroplast  surface geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    11    9     99
## 3 To       mitochondria volume  geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    10    9     50
## 4 To       mitochondria surface geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    10    9     52
## 5 To       vacuole      volume  geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe     6    6     25
## 6 To       vacuole      surface geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe     6    6     28
## 7 Tp       chloroplast  volume  geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   11     64
## 8 Tp       chloroplast  surface geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   11     65
## 9 Tp       mitochondria volume  geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   11     80
## 10 Tp      mitochondria surface geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   11     81
## 11 Tp       vacuole      volume  geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe     8    8     55
## 12 Tp       vacuole      surface geo_cal 100_Fe 5_Fe     8    8     57
## # i 3 more variables: p <dbl>, p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>

```


chloroplast mitochondria media

chloroplast mitochondria chloroplast mitochondria

t_test for means

A tibble: 12 x 13

```

## media organelle geometric .y. group1 group2 n1 n2 statistic df
## <fct> <fct> <fct> <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 100_Fe chloroplast volume geo_~ To Tp 11 11 1.74 15.1
## 2 100_Fe chloroplast surface geo_~ To Tp 11 11 5.66 19.3
## 3 100_Fe mitochondria volume geo_~ To Tp 10 11 -5.58 16.1
## 4 100_Fe mitochondria surface geo_~ To Tp 10 11 -6.18 16.8
## 5 100_Fe vacuole volume geo_~ To Tp 6 8 -0.235 11.0
## 6 100_Fe vacuole surface geo_~ To Tp 6 8 -0.0442 8.72
## 7 5_Fe chloroplast volume geo_~ To Tp 9 11 -2.11 17.5
## 8 5_Fe chloroplast surface geo_~ To Tp 9 11 -0.151 15.1
## 9 5_Fe mitochondria volume geo_~ To Tp 9 11 -3.64 17.9
## 10 5_Fe mitochondria surface geo_~ To Tp 9 11 -5.30 13.3
## 11 5_Fe vacuole volume geo_~ To Tp 6 8 1.60 11.9
## 12 5_Fe vacuole surface geo_~ To Tp 6 8 0.519 11.0
## # i 3 more variables: p <dbl>, p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>

```


organelle █ chloroplast █ mitochondria genotype Tc

organelle chloroplast mitoch

organelle chloroplast mitocho

Statistical tests

Normality and variance homogeneity tests

Shapiro-Wilk normality test:

```
## # A tibble: 4 x 7
##   genotype media variable    statistic      p p.adj p.signif
##   <fct>    <fct> <chr>          <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr>
## 1 To      100_Fe chloro_mito    0.948 0.640 0.640 ns
## 2 To      5_Fe   chloro_mito    0.881 0.162 0.487 ns
## 3 Tp      100_Fe chloro_mito    0.913 0.267 0.533 ns
## 4 Tp      5_Fe   chloro_mito    0.861 0.0591 0.237 ns
```

Variance test:

```
##   genotype  p_value p_signif p_adj p_adj_signif
## 1 To +/-Fe 0.0005366    ***   NA
## 2 Tp +/-Fe 0.0005366    ***   NA
```

t_test for means

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 11
##   genotype .y.      group1 group2   n1   n2 statistic   df      p   p.adj
##   <fct>    <chr>    <chr> <chr> <int> <int>   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 To      chloro_mito 100_Fe 5_Fe    10    9     6.41  15.9 9  e-6 1.80e-5
## 2 Tp      chloro_mito 100_Fe 5_Fe    11   11    -1.13  16.7 2.76e-1 2.76e-1
## # i 1 more variable: p.signif <chr>
```


notype To media 100_otype Tp media 100_

##Surface to volume ratios:

```
## # A tibble: 6 x 8
## # Groups:   experiment, test, time, phase, genotype, media, organelle [6]
```

```

## experiment test time phase genotype media organelle ratio
## <fct> <fct> <dbl> <chr> <fct> <fct> <fct> <dbl>
## 1 1 1 72 f Tp 5_Fe cell 3.62
## 2 1 1 72 f Tp 5_Fe vacuole 2.16
## 3 1 1 72 f Tp 5_Fe nucleus 4.23
## 4 1 1 72 f Tp 5_Fe chloroplast 4.00
## 5 1 1 72 f Tp 5_Fe mitochondria 9.90
## 6 1 1 72 f Tp 5_Fe pyrenoid 9.09

```

Statistical tests

Normality and variance homogeneity tests

Shapiro-Wilk normality test:

```

## # A tibble: 4 x 7
## genotype media variable statistic p p.adj p.signif
## <fct> <fct> <chr> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr>
## 1 To 100_Fe ratio 0.922 0.335 1 ns
## 2 To 5_Fe ratio 0.938 0.563 1 ns
## 3 Tp 100_Fe ratio 0.960 0.772 1 ns
## 4 Tp 5_Fe ratio 0.895 0.161 0.642 ns

```

Variance test:

```

## genotype p_value p_signif p_adj p_adj_signif
## 1 To +/-Fe 0.9435 NA
## 2 Tp +/-Fe 0.9435 NA

```

t_test for means

```

## # A tibble: 6 x 12
## genotype organelle .y. group1 group2 n1 n2 statistic df p
## <fct> <fct> <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 To chloroplast ratio 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 9 -0.934 11.2 0.37
## 2 To mitochondria ratio 100_Fe 5_Fe 10 9 -0.967 17.0 0.347
## 3 To cell ratio 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 9 -2.18 17.4 0.0432
## 4 Tp chloroplast ratio 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 11 -4.03 19.0 0.000709
## 5 Tp mitochondria ratio 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 11 -1.24 19.7 0.231
## 6 Tp cell ratio 100_Fe 5_Fe 11 11 -1.21 19.4 0.24
## # i 2 more variables: p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>

```


chloroplast media E

mitochondria media I

chloroplast media E

mitochondria media I

■ chloroplast
 ■ mitochondria
 media
 100_

t_test for means

```

## # A tibble: 6 x 12
##   media organelle   .y. group1 group2   n1   n2 statistic   df         p
##   <fct> <fct>      <chr> <chr> <chr> <int> <int>   <dbl> <dbl>   <dbl>
## 1 100_Fe chloroplast ratio To     Tp      11    11     5.40  18.5   3.61e-5
## 2 100_Fe mitochondria ratio To     Tp     10    11    -7.35  18.3   7.19e-7
## 3 100_Fe cell        ratio To     Tp     11    11    -2.93  20.0   8.3 e-3
## 4 5_Fe   chloroplast ratio To     Tp      9     11     1.71  10.9   1.15e-1
## 5 5_Fe   mitochondria ratio To     Tp      9     11    -7.54  18.0   5.65e-7
## 6 5_Fe   cell        ratio To     Tp      9     11    -1.69  18.0   1.09e-1
## # i 2 more variables: p.adj <dbl>, p.signif <chr>

```


■ chloroplast
 ■ mitochondria
 media
 ○ 100_Fe

mitochondria
 media
 ○ 5_Fe